

Strong localized pumping of water vapor to high altitudes on Mars during the perihelion season

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Key Points:

- Latitudinal distributions of water vapor up to 120 km are analyzed in detail using NOMAD observations with an improved retrieval scheme.
- Water vapor injection during the perihelion localized around 50°-60° S in three consecutive Martian years.
- Martian year 34 Global Dust Storm may have affected the driving mechanisms of the plume, delaying its appearance and reducing its magnitude.

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Abstract

Here we present water vapor vertical profiles observed with the ExoMars TGO/NOMAD instrument during the perihelion and Southern summer solstice season ($L_S = 240^\circ$ - 300°) in three consecutive Martian Years 34, 35 and 36. We show the detailed latitudinal distribution of H_2O at tangent altitudes from 10 to 120 km, revealing a vertical plume at $60^\circ S$ - $50^\circ S$ injecting H_2O upward, reaching abundance of about 50 ppmv at 100 km. We have observed this event repeatedly in the three Martian years analyzed, appearing at $L_S = 260^\circ - 280^\circ$ and showing inter-annual variations in the magnitude and timing due to long term effects of the MY 34 Global Dust Storm. We provide a rough estimate of projected hydrogen escape of $3.2 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ associated to these plumes, adding further evidence of the key role played by the perihelion season in the long term evolution of the planet's climate.

Plain Language Summary

Studying the vertical distribution of the Martian atmosphere is crucial to understand what happened to the water presumably present in larger abundance on ancient Mars. We have analyzed the vertical profiles of three Martian Years during the Southern summer, revealing a strong vertical transport of water vapor to the upper atmosphere. This seasonal phenomenon seems to be repeated annually, although with variations in the location and time of the year. Our estimation of the associated upward hydrogen flux represents an important loss which could have contributed to the escape of water to space for at least the period in which Mars had its present orbital inclination.

1 Introduction

The thin atmosphere we observe at Mars nowadays makes the planet cold and dry. In an atmosphere dominated by CO_2 , water vapor only represents a small fraction of the total atmospheric composition ($\sim 0.03\%$). Spacecraft observations have provided valuable insights into the H_2O behavior on Mars. In the current Martian climate, H_2O shows a large variability throughout the year involving sublimation and condensation processes affected by dust and atmospheric transport (Montmessin et al., 2017). This cycle is also known to present strong latitudinal gradients, as reported by the Thermal Emission Spectrometer (TES) by using column densities (Smith, 2002). However, until the last decade, the knowledge about the water vapor vertical structure and the latitudinal variations at high altitudes was limited. Solar occultation (SO) observations allowed to explore the atmospheric vertical distribution in unprecedented detail. A few instruments, the Spectroscopy for the Investigation of the Characteristics of the Atmosphere of Mars (SPICAM) onboard Mars Express (MEX) and Auguste onboard the Phobos-2, have provided vertical profiles of the martian atmosphere using SO observations (Fedorova et al., 2009; Maltagliati et al., 2011, 2013; Fedorova et al., 2018, 2021) and others, the Compact Reconnaissance Imaging Spectrometer for Mars (CRISM) and the Mars Climate Sounder (MCS), both on board Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO) used limb observations for indirect information on H_2O abundance (Clancy et al., 2012, 2017; Heavens et al., 2018).

The first SO and water vapor vertical profiles on Mars were obtained with the Auguste spectrometer (Rodin et al., 1997). With SPICAM and mostly limited to an altitude below 70 km, some of the first dedicated studies on H_2O vertical profiles were done by Fedorova et al. (2009). Later, Maltagliati et al. (2011) and Maltagliati et al. (2013) reported evidence of H_2O present in excess of saturation (supersaturation) during the Northern summer and showed for the first time H_2O vertical profiles during a full Martian Year (MY). They found a strong variability of the profiles and reported discrepancies with General Circulation Models (GCMs). More recently, (Fedorova et al., 2021) presented the first multiyear survey of water vapor vertical distribution obtained from SPICAM observations.

Similarly, Clancy et al. (2017) analyzed the seasonal and global variability of H_2O profiles which were derived from CRISM O_2 emission rates. They claimed difficulties in the accuracy

75 of modeling cloud microphysics in Mars GCM simulations.

76 Later, Fedorova et al. (2018) reported an enhancement of the H₂O abundance in the middle
77 atmosphere during the 2007 dust storm and Chaffin et al. (2017) showed how this led to an
78 increase of the escape rates of hydrogen. This was also studied by (Heavens et al., 2018)
79 using estimates of middle atmospheric water vapor and ice content from the distribution
80 of water ice clouds and temperature observed with MCS. This phenomenon was observed
81 again during the 2018 Global Dust Storm (GDS) with the Nadir and Occultation for MArs
82 Discovery (NOMAD) and Atmospheric Chemistry Suite (ACS) instruments, both onboard
83 the ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter (TGO) (Alday et al., 2021; Aoki et al., 2019, 2022; Belyaev
84 et al., 2021; Brines et al., 2023; Fedorova et al., 2020, 2023; Vandaele et al., 2019; Villanueva
85 et al., 2021) and also with the SPICAM instrument, whose observations were compared to
86 the GDS of MY 28 (Fedorova et al., 2021). These recent works analyzed H₂O vertical
87 distribution up to 100 km thanks to the high sensitivity of the instruments.

88 Aoki et al. (2019), Vandaele et al. (2019) and Fedorova et al. (2020) reported an increase in
89 the H₂O abundance between 40-80 km during the GDS, the latter showing dust playing a
90 significant role in altering atmospheric dynamics during dust storms. These events lift dust
91 particles into the atmosphere modifying the temperature profiles due to the dust radiative
92 heating (Neary et al., 2020) and preventing H₂O condensation even at high altitudes,
93 enhancing hydrogen escape (Heavens et al., 2018). Belyaev et al. (2021) presented profiles
94 in the upper mesosphere reporting similar water abundance during the GDS and perihelion
95 periods. Brines et al. (2023) showed the effects of the GDS comparing the southern spring
96 season during MYs 34 and 35 and reported supersaturation events in presence of water
97 ice, a phenomenon also found by Fedorova et al. (2020, 2023). This is in line with the
98 study presented by Poncin et al. (2022), in which on average, large parts of the atmosphere
99 were observed to be close to saturation, although typically at lower altitudes than those
100 observed by Fedorova et al. (2023). Villanueva et al. (2021) reported an increase of the
101 H₂O in both abundance and altitude during the beginning of the Southern summer, but
102 they only retrieved H₂O up to 100 km for one MY and did not focus the analysis on this
103 feature, as done in this paper. This localized phenomenon was studied by Shaposhnikov
104 et al. (2019), who modeled mechanisms responsible for the upward water transport at
105 high southern latitudes during the perihelion season. The injection of water during this
106 season was previously noticed by SPICAM during multi-annual monitoring (Fedorova et al.,
107 2021), where they observed H₂O at high altitudes repeatedly during the Southern summer,
108 confirming a seasonal impact on the hydrogen escape rate.

109 Here, building upon previous NOMAD water vapor retrievals from Brines et al. (2023), we
110 introduced several improvements which provide H₂O with an optimal vertical resolution
111 from about 10 to 120 km. This work analyzes with an unprecedented detail the vertical
112 distribution of H₂O during the perihelion ($L_S \sim 250^\circ$) and Southern summer solstice
113 ($L_S \sim 270^\circ$) of three consecutive MYs, which besides the dust storms, is claimed to be
114 the season driving the escape of hydrogen to space (Jakosky, 2021; Mayyasi et al., 2023).
115 We focused the analysis on the upper mesosphere, showing for the first time latitudinal
116 structures from 60 to 120 km.

117 The NOMAD instrument and the data analysis are described in Section 2. In Text S1
118 of Supporting Information (SI) we provide information about the parameterization of the
119 NOMAD SO characterization. Details about the methodology used during the data analysis
120 are presented in Texts S2, S3 and S4 of SI. The main results are presented in Section 3.
121 Extended interpretation of the observations and conclusion are given in Sections 4 and 5
122 respectively. In Text S5 of SI we show a comparison of three Forward Models (FMs), used
123 to perform an internal validation of the NOMAD characterization and its implementation
124 into the simulations.

125 2 Data analysis

126 The NOMAD instrument is a suite of three spectrometers (channels) covering spectral
127 regions between 0.2 to 4.3 μm . It observes the Martian atmosphere with three channels in

different geometries: Solar Occultation (SO) and limb/nadir observation (LNO). A third channel observes the atmosphere in both configurations (UVIS). Each channel is equipped with its own set of optics and detectors (Vandaele et al., 2018). The SO channel operates in the infrared covering a spectral range between 2.3 to 4.3 μm (2320 - 4350 cm^{-1}) using an echelle grating in Littrow configuration with a resolving power around 17000. NOMAD uses an Acousto-Optical Tunable Filter (AOTF) to separate diffraction orders on the detector plane. In addition, the dispersion and diffraction effects of the light throughout the whole optical system affects the signal reaching the detector introducing an instrumental effect to the spectral lines. Typically, the Instrumental Line Shape (ILS) can be modeled by convolving the monochromatic spectrum with a Gaussian kernel. However, the NOMAD data exhibits an asymmetric ILS with an extended left wing of the Gaussian. This feature can be instead reproduced with a double Gaussian whose separation varies with frequency and diffraction order (Thomas et al., 2022; Villanueva, Liuzzi, Aoki, et al., 2022). More details about the NOMAD AOTF and ILS characterization are summarized in Text S1 of SI.

For this study we selected 1065 occultations taken with the NOMAD SO channel. The selected observations cover the perihelion and the Southern summer solstice season of three consecutive MYs (34, 35 and 36) with Solar Longitude (L_S) ranging from $L_S = 240^\circ$ to $L_S = 300^\circ$. The seasonal-latitudinal distribution of the occultations is shown in Fig. 1E.

We used Level 1 calibrated transmittances processed by the Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB) (Trompet et al., 2023), which were revised by our in-house pipeline to clean them from residual spectral shifts and bendings at each altitude. The IAA-preprocessing includes the latest NOMAD instrument characterization (Villanueva, Liuzzi, Aoki, et al., 2022) and uses the state-of-the-art line-by-line Karlsruhe Optimized Radiative transfer Algorithm (KOPRA) during the cleaning (Brines et al., 2023; Lopez-Valverde et al., 2022).

For the inversions we selected spectra from the NOMAD diffraction orders 134 (3011-3035 cm^{-1}) and 136 (3056-3081 cm^{-1}) both containing lines with intensities of about $10^{-21} \text{cm}^{-1}/(\text{molecule} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2})$, and from orders 168 (3775-3805 cm^{-1}) and 169 (3798-3828 cm^{-1}), these two with stronger line intensities of about $10^{-19} \text{cm}^{-1}/(\text{molecule} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2})$ from the ν_3 fundamental band. These line intensity and their broadening coefficients used in this study are defined for the standard HITRAN atmosphere (1 atm, 296 K) (Gordon et al., 2022). Although those coefficients are given for air (Earth atmosphere), we performed sensitivity tests comparing KOPRA simulations using the default HITRAN linelist and the list provided by Gamache et al. (2016) for its application to CO₂-rich atmospheres. Our results showed that at the optically thin region of the diffraction orders used in this work, the differences in transmittance between both simulations was below the measurement noise ($< 10^{-4}$). Therefore, we decided to use the latest linelist available from Gordon et al. (2022) with standard H₂O line parameters.

Considering this, we used spectra from orders 134 and 136 for the lower atmosphere and from orders 168 and 169 for the upper atmosphere, typically covering an altitude range from 0 to 60 km and from 60 to 120 km respectively. This way, following a similar approach as in Brines et al. (2023) we extended their methodology from two to four diffraction orders using different orders for different altitude ranges in order to avoid optically thick (saturated) absorption lines present in orders 168 and 169 at low altitudes. We improved our retrieval scheme in three ways.

First, we optimized our pipeline in order to handle two diffraction orders simultaneously. Before we were combining two separate inversions, one for each diffraction order, as if they were different measurements. Now, we perform a common global fit of the spectra in the two diffraction orders at once. The selected occultations contain pairs of diffraction orders with at least one of the low altitude orders (134, 136) and one of the high altitude orders (168, 169). This is the optimal way to combine diffraction orders which sample different altitude ranges, avoiding artifacts and ad-hoc assumptions in the transition regions. Details about the combination of orders are presented in Text S2 of SI.

Second, and in support of the previous point, we introduced an automatic selection of the

183 transition region for the merging of the low/high altitude diffraction orders. This is based
 184 on a computation of the altitude where the H₂O lines become optically thick, analyzing how
 185 the shape of the absorption lines observed by NOMAD changes with altitude in orders 168
 186 and 169.

187 And third, we developed an in-house tool to improve the characterization of the NOMAD
 188 SO measurement noise. This is necessary because our retrieval scheme is optimized to
 189 assume the measurement uncertainties as pure uncorrelated random noise. However, the
 190 uncertainties provided within the Level 1 calibrated data (Thomas et al., 2022) do not
 191 differentiate between systematic and random noise. In order to quantify and correct for
 192 the systematic component, we performed an analysis of the spectra at every SO using
 193 covariance matrices, allowing us to characterize the random noise of the data. As a result,
 194 we are improving the sensitivity and performance of the inversions in the upper atmosphere
 195 (90-120 km). A description of the measurement noise characterization is presented in Text
 196 S3 of SI.

197 Using the modification previously described we managed to improve the retrieved water
 198 vapor, obtaining continuous vertical profiles with better vertical resolution compared to
 199 the results from (Brines et al., 2023), typically ~ 2 km (larger than the NOMAD field
 200 of view (Vandaele et al., 2018)). Specifically, as shown in Fig. S1 (panels F and G)
 201 this improvement can be seen around the transition region from the lower to the upper
 202 atmosphere (50-70 km). We performed the inversion of the selected dataset following
 203 the convergence criteria presented in Brines et al. (2023). The retrievals were performed
 204 using the Retrieval Control Program (RCP) developed at the Institut für Meteorologie und
 205 Klimaforschung (IMK) which incorporates KOPRA as FM. For the a priori atmosphere we
 206 followed the same approach presented in Brines et al. (2023). That is, during the retrieval
 207 process we used total atmospheric densities and temperature-pressure profiles derived from
 208 specific runs of the Mars Planetary Climate Model (Forget et al., 1999) developed at the
 209 Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique (LMD Mars PCM) at the exact location and time
 210 of the NOMAD observations. As discussed in Brines et al. (2023), our H₂O retrieval scheme
 211 has low sensitivity to changes in temperature profiles. We performed several sensitivity tests
 212 in order to estimate the expected errors due to our PCM assumption. Performing retrievals
 213 changing the apriori temperature profile by ± 5 K had an impact of 2% on the retrieved
 214 water vapor VMR while introducing an oscillation in the pressure profile with an amplitude
 215 of 10% had an overall impact of less than 4% in the retrieved water vapor number density.
 216 During the inversion we used a first order Tikhonov-type regularization optimized for each
 217 diffraction order.

218 A precise FM requires a precise characterization of the instrumental response. Since Brines
 219 et al. (2023), we are implementing the latest description of the NOMAD SO (Villanueva,
 220 Liuzzi, Aoki, et al., 2022). With the objective of validating this implementation and to
 221 unify the criteria used by other teams within the NOMAD consortium, we performed an
 222 extensive comparison of the FMs used by the main groups actively analyzing H₂O on Mars
 223 with NOMAD SO data. These teams are: Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía (IAA-
 224 CSIC), Tokyo University, Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (ISAB-BIRA), and
 225 NASA Goddard Spaceflight Center. This work revealed a remarkable agreement between the
 226 FM used by the teams, showing discrepancies below 0.2% when comparing high resolution
 227 simulations. A summary is presented in Text S5 of SI.

229 **3 Results**

230 **3.1 Latitudinal Variation**

231 The eccentricity of the Martian orbit is known to significantly enhance the solar flux
 232 reaching the planet during the perihelion season (Smith et al., 2017), enhancing the wind
 233 stress near the surface and the lifting of dust, which in turn absorbs more solar radiation and
 234 heats the atmosphere, making the Southern summer ($L_S = 270^\circ - 360^\circ$) the warmest and

235 most humid season on Mars. This affects the meridional circulation and vertical transport
 236 of water vapor, both being intensified during this season. As mentioned in Section 1,
 237 during the perihelion season there are strong gradients in the latitudinal distribution of
 238 water column abundance. In order to explore its vertical structure, we studied different L_S
 239 periods through the southern spring and summer seasons. We selected observations during
 240 and after the perihelion season, covering L_S ranges $L_S = 240^\circ - 260^\circ$, $L_S = 260^\circ - 280^\circ$
 241 and $L_S = 280^\circ - 300^\circ$ (denoted L_S^1 , L_S^2 and L_S^3 respectively) of MYs 34, 35 and 36.
 242 The latitudinal distribution of H_2O is presented in Fig. 1. We have binned the retrieved
 243 profiles in 5° latitude intervals. The bins were calculated with a weighted average of all the
 244 profiles within the interval, according to its retrieved uncertainty. Due to the TGO orbital
 245 configuration, the L_S^2 range of MY 34 observations is different from the range selected for
 246 MYs 35 and 36. The selected ranges optimize the latitudinal coverage. During these L_S
 247 periods, we observed a vertical column of H_2O (denoted as "plume") with abundance about
 248 50 ppmv at $60^\circ S - 30^\circ S$ reaching altitudes up to 100 km during L_S^2 in MYs 35 and 36 (Fig.
 249 1B2, 1C2). MY 34 also showed a similar structure but with reduced abundance and with a
 250 peak showing up later in time (Fig. 1A3, 1D). In the three MYs, NOMAD observations do
 251 not reveal any significant water injection above 80 km prior to $L_S \sim 260^\circ$ (Fig. 1A1, 1B1,
 252 1C1). In the Northern hemisphere, the H_2O obtained is mostly confined below 40 km and
 253 at low-mid latitudes, as expected during the winter season (Montmessin et al., 2017).
 254 We compared our H_2O results with data derived from ACS MIR observations obtained
 255 during L_S^2 and L_S^3 in MYs 34 and 35 (Belyaev et al., 2021), revealing a good agreement
 256 between both instruments. This is presented in Figure S4 of SI, showing the H_2O number
 257 density seasonal variation observed with NOMAD and ACS at 80 and 100 km.
 258

259 3.2 Interannual Variability

260 Although we found a strong injection of water vapor to high altitudes in the three
 261 MYs, we observed some differences between them. In order to evaluate the contribution of
 262 the injection and its interannual variability, we averaged the retrieved profiles within the
 263 solar longitude ranges L_S^1 , L_S^2 and L_S^3 for each analyzed MY, excluding observations from
 264 latitudes below 45° in order to capture vertical profiles representative of the observed plume.
 265 The average H_2O profiles for each L_S range in the southern hemisphere are presented in Fig.
 266 2 for MYs 34 (A), 35 (B) and 36 (C). The difference in ppmv between L_S^2 and L_S^3 profiles is
 267 shown in panel D. We observed a clear enhancement of the water abundance above 80 km
 268 of about 30 ppmv during L_S^2 in MYs 35 and 36 (orange and green lines), showing a similar
 269 vertical structure in both years. In contrast, MY 34 shows an enhancement of about 15
 270 ppm during L_S^3 due to the peak observed around $L_S \sim 285^\circ$. The vertical profiles observed
 271 during the period L_S^1 (green line) prior to the plume detection show a similar trend in the
 272 three MYs.

273 4 Discussion

274 Recent works reporting TGO SO measurements found high water vapor abundance during
 275 the season analyzed here. Belyaev et al. (2021) using the ACS MIR channel found peaks
 276 of about 10-30 ppmv of H_2O at 100-120 km around Mars perihelion in MYs 34 and 35;
 277 as well as (Fedorova et al., 2023), where the maximum was found up to 100 km. Using
 278 NOMAD SO data, Aoki et al. (2022) observed a maximum H_2O density at $L_S = 265^\circ$
 279 in MY 35; Brines et al. (2023) using NOMAD SO observations showed H_2O abundance about
 280 50 ppmv at high altitudes around $L_S \sim 260^\circ$ in MY 35 and Villanueva et al. (2021), again
 281 exploiting NOMAD SO measurements during MYs 34 and 35 denominated this feature as
 282 "Aspirator". We report here a detailed latitudinal structure of this phenomenon during
 283 three consecutive MYs for the first time, with a robust characterization of the observations
 284 in the upper mesosphere (>100 km) and revealing a large H_2O column located at $60^\circ S$
 285 reaching altitudes up to 110 km. This plume appears during MYs 34, 35 and 36 (Fig. 1A,

Figure 1. Water vapor latitudinal variation during $L_S^1=240^\circ-260^\circ$ (A1, B1, C1), $L_S^2=260^\circ-280^\circ$ (A2, B2, C2) and $L_S^3=280^\circ-300^\circ$ (A3, B3, C3) for MYs 34 (left), 35 (middle) and 36 (right). Lines show VMR contours at 100 (black), 50 (gray) and 20 (white) ppmv. Dots in panels A1-A3, B1-B3, C1-C3 indicate the latitude, Solar Longitude and Local Solar Time of the observations. Panel D shows the seasonal variation of water vapor number density (cm⁻³) in the southern hemisphere at 100 km for $L_S = 240^\circ-300^\circ$ during MYs 34 (blue), 35 (orange) and 36 (green). Vertical dashed line indicates the peak of the plume observed at 100 km during MYs 35 and 36 at $L_S = 268^\circ$. Solid lines show the seasonal average. Panel E shows the latitude of the analyzed NOMAD SO observations over solar longitude for MYs 34 (blue), 35 (orange) and 36 (green). Horizontal dashed line indicates the equator. In panels D and E, morning and evening terminator occultations are indicated with circles and triangles respectively

Figure 2. Averaged water vapor VMR profiles at southern hemisphere during solar longitude ranges $L_S^1 = 240^\circ - 260^\circ$ (green), $L_S^2 = 260^\circ - 280^\circ$ (yellow) and $L_S^3 = 280 - 300^\circ$ (blue) for MYs 34(A), 35(B), and 36(C). Profiles from latitudes below 45° have been excluded in the average. Shaded areas represent the standard deviation of the average. Vertical dashed lines indicate abundance of 50 ppmv. Panel D shows the averaged profiles difference $L_S^2 - L_S^3$ for MYs 34 (blue), 35 (orange) and 36 (green). Vertical dotted lines indicate abundance of ± 30 ppmv (dotted) and 0 ppmv (dashed) for reference.

287 atmosphere repeatedly every year during a specific period of time (L_S^2). Observations prior
 288 to $L_S = 260^\circ$ (L_S^1) do not show any significant injection but a gradual increase in water
 289 vapor in southern latitudes starting around $L_S = 250^\circ$, specially during MYs 35 and 36
 290 (Fig. 1D). However, in MY 34 this phenomenon is observed later in time (L_S^3) and presents
 291 a lower abundance plume, with 50 ppmv at 80 km and < 20 ppmv at 100 km (Fig. 1A3).
 292 This feature, reaching altitudes close to the mesopause (~ 120 km), can not be simulated by
 293 the current LMD Mars PCM (Forget et al., 1999), which was used to generate the apriori
 294 climatology used during the retrievals presented here. However, it seems to coincide in time
 295 and location with an upward H_2O flux branch in the model by Shaposhnikov et al. (2019).
 296 Nonetheless, simulations using data assimilation (DA) (Holmes et al., 2022) showed the
 297 presence of the plume during L_S^2 of MY 35. The assimilation combined the Mars PCM Uk-
 298 spectral with several spacecraft datasets, including NOMAD water vapor column abundance
 299 (Crismani et al., 2021) and NOMAD+ACS water vapor profiles (Alday et al., 2021; Aoki et
 300 al., 2019; Villanueva et al., 2021; Fedorova et al., 2020), proving the advantages of combining
 301 GCM models with observations. Regardless of this result, firm conclusions about the nature
 302 of this feature cannot be drawn solely from DA studies. Future studies with a free GCM
 303 focusing on exploring its response to diverse parameters' perturbations shall provide valuable
 304 information about the drivers of this unique feature. DA profiles are shown in Figure S8 of
 305 SI.

306 The discrepancy between MYs 35, 36 and MY 34 might be attributed to several reasons.
 307 One is related to the NOMAD sampling and its orbital configuration. The TGO coverage
 308 during MY 34 is different compared to the sampling during MYs 35 and 36, this is, TGO
 309 sampled the same latitudes at different L_S . If the plume had a preferential latitude to appear
 310 every year, NOMAD would not observe it at the same L_S during MY 34 than during MYs
 311 35 and 36. This suggests the H_2O injection observed here to be a local and a short duration
 312 phenomenon taking place in a specific time and location. This difference between MY 34
 313 and the following Mars Years is observed in Fig. 1D, where the peak of the plume in MYs
 314 35 and 36 occurs at $L_S \sim 268^\circ$, a period of time which was not sampled by TGO during
 315 MY 34. Aoki et al. (2022) also reported a H_2O peak at $L_S = 265^\circ$ during MY 35 but not
 316 in MY 34, attributing this to differences in the NOMAD sampling.

317 Another possible cause of the interannual variability may be the alteration of the atmospheric
 318 dynamics and transport caused by the MY 34 GDS and its slow decay phase in southern
 319 extratropic latitudes at $L_S \sim 255^\circ$ (Kass et al., 2020). The water vapor abundance peak
 320 observed later in time at $L_S \sim 285^\circ$ suggests a delay in the appearance of the plume during
 321 MY 34. In addition, the abundance below 60 km during MY 34 in the southern hemisphere

322 prior to $L_S = 260^\circ$ show smaller values than in MYs 35 and 36. This circumstance can be
 323 observed also in Aoki et al. (2022) (see their figures 8 and 9), although they did not discuss
 324 this interannual difference. Fedorova et al. (2023) also reported much higher water vapor
 325 saturation during the perihelion of MY 35 compared to MY 34 and our observations are also
 326 compatible with Pankine et al. (2023). They studied the water vapor in the Southern Polar
 327 Region (SPR) analyzing observations of several instruments during years with and without
 328 global dust events, claiming that water vapor column abundance decreased following the
 329 GDS, when compared to years without a GDS. During the period L_S^1 , the temperature
 330 (Fedorova et al., 2023) and the column dust optical depth (Martín-Rubio et al., 2024) at
 331 high southern latitudes were similar in both MY 34 and 35 (see their Fig. 7 and Fig. 2
 332 respectively), which may exclude the possibility of an enhanced water vapor condensation
 333 during the GDS year. Hence, the cause of the water abundance deficit during MY 34 may
 334 be related to a lower water vapor production rate by sublimation of the H_2O ice reservoirs.
 335 Due to the GDS, the southern polar vortex diminished its intensity during $L_S = 200^\circ - 220^\circ$,
 336 providing a weaker barrier to transport into the SPR and onto the surface (Streeter et al.,
 337 2021). This phenomena, could have increased the deposition of dust over H_2O ice during the
 338 GDS peak activity, leading to a reduction of the water vapor production rate (Gundlach et
 339 al., 2011). Pankine et al. (2023) also suggested the disruption of the southward transport of
 340 vapor by the atmospheric circulation as a potential cause of the observed differences between
 341 GDS and non-GDS years.

342 These observations may suggest that, in addition to the strong upward branch of the
 343 meridional circulation (Shaposhnikov et al., 2019), the mechanisms driving the formation
 344 of the plume require a sufficiently high tropospheric (< 50 km) water vapor abundance at
 345 least larger than 100 ppm. In MY 34 this condition is fulfilled during L_S^2 , leading to the
 346 delayed plume observed during L_S^3 . This hypothesis should be explored in future studies
 347 with the help of observations from multiple instruments combined with GCMs (Holmes et
 348 al., 2022).

349 Note that the measurements during L_S^2 of MYs 35 and 36 correspond to the evening
 350 terminator, whereas the measurements during L_S^3 of these same years correspond to the morning
 351 terminator. This can be observed in Fig. 1D, where the peak in H_2O density at $L_S \sim 285^\circ$
 352 only in MY 34 appears during evening observations. At present, we can not exclude local
 353 time effects as partially responsible for the plume origin and variability.

354 In addition to the vertical transport of H_2O in the plume, effects of the meridional transport
 355 towards Northern latitudes at high altitudes can also be observed in Fig. 1B2 and 1C2,
 356 showing a layer of H_2O at 100 km with abundance >20 ppmv reaching latitudes of about
 357 30°N . As the Southern summer advances and the vertical transport around 60°S weakens,
 358 the ascending plume vanishes and the vertical and meridional injections of water diminishes.
 359 This effect is observed in panels B3 and C3 of Fig. 1, where abundance at high altitudes
 360 decrease in both hemispheres, suggesting a less efficient northward transport.

362 Average H_2O profiles in Fig. 2 present an enhancement of water above 50 km in the
 363 southern hemisphere during L_S^2 of MYs 35 and 36. As seen in panels B and C of Fig. 2,
 364 it appears repeatedly in both years, showing a difference of 20-30 ppmv at 100 km between
 365 the two analyzed L_S periods. In contrast, in Fig. 2A this difference is smaller during MY
 366 34, with larger abundance during L_S^3 and showing a variation of about 15 ppmv above 80
 367 km between both L_S ranges. We can use these averaged profiles to estimate the atomic
 368 hydrogen escape flux associated to the plumes studied here. Applying the model by Chaffin
 369 et al. (2017) and assuming that the water injection from Fig. 2B and 2C is sustained
 370 during the whole period when the plume is observed ($\sim 20^\circ$ in L_S , i.e. 10^6 s), we obtained
 371 an integral escape flux about $\sim 3.2 \pm 0.5 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, which is in a similar range as
 372 previous results (Belyaev et al., 2021; Bhattacharyya et al., 2017; Holmes et al., 2021).
 373 Repeating this exercise for the period when the plume was not observed, we obtained an
 374 estimation of $\sim 2.5 \pm 0.3 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. Taking into account the uncertainties introduced
 375 in the estimation of the escape ($\sim 15\%$) and the possible bias due to the uncertainties
 376 of the thermal structure within the region where the profiles were averaged ($\sim 5\%$ as a

conservative value obtained from our sensitivity tests), we estimate a rough increase by $\sim 30 \pm 25\%$ in the hydrogen escape over the period without the plume, which represents a modest but not negligible increase marginally above our uncertainties. Details about the method used for the estimation are presented in Text S4 of SI. This estimation contains several uncertainties and the calculation presented here is only suitable to provide a rough order of magnitude estimate. Testing the known or unknown approximations in Chaffin et al. (2017) photochemical model was not a target of the present work. More recently, Montmessin et al. (2022) used a hybrid photochemistry-transport model combined with ACS observations from Belyaev et al. (2021) to compare the hydrogen escape rate during the perihelion season of MYs 34 and 35, suggesting this season to dominate the long term escape.

5 Conclusions

During perihelion, suspended dust particles alter the thermal structure and consequently the atmospheric dynamics. This directly affects the atmospheric composition by strong vertical transport of minor species like H_2O . This work provides an insight into the water vapor vertical distribution during the perihelion and Southern summer solstice season. We have presented detailed latitudinal variation of the H_2O showing a strong pumping of water into the upper atmosphere and revealing abundance with volume mixing ratios about 50 ppmv at 100 km. The water vapor plume is observed to be confined to the southern hemisphere at latitudes between 60° and 50° . In addition, we have observed this feature only during a short period of time (20° in L_S) but repeated during the three MYs analyzed here. During non-GDS years we observe the injection to occur at $L_S = 260^\circ - 280^\circ$. However, during MY 34 the plume appears shifted towards southern latitudes and appears later in time, showing lower abundance above 80 km. We attributed these differences to variations in the latitudinal and seasonal sampling of the TGO spacecraft and to possible long term effects of the MY 34 GDS weakening the southern polar vortex and allowing the dust to deposit over water ice reservoirs, leading to a reduced water vapor production rate during the perihelion. In order to answer these questions, more observations of this phenomenon will be necessary. Increasing the number of H_2O dedicated observations with TGO during the perihelion season could help to provide a better temporal and latitudinal sampling of this short term and local event. We are planning to learn about possible drivers of this phenomenon by exploring the response of the Mars PCM to diverse parameters' perturbations, study that will be presented in future works. Finally, we provided a rough estimation of the hydrogen escape flux associated to the strong plumes in MY35 and 36 of about $\sim 3.2 \pm 0.5 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which adds to the importance of the perihelion season to the global budget of hydrogen escape on Mars. The accumulation of more MYs of observations may give us a good estimate of the importance of these plumes over the global and annual hydrogen escape on Mars. Our results are in line with those presented in previous similar analysis. A comparison with Belyaev et al. (2021) presented in SI shows a good agreement in the H_2O abundance retrieved with NOMAD and ACS instruments, complementing and confirming many of Belyaev et al. (2021) findings with a different instrument and retrieval approach.

420 **Open Research Section**

421 The NOMAD SO Level 1a calibrated data used in this work are available at the
422 European Space Agency Planetary Science Archive (*PSA*, 2024). More information about
423 the data on the PSA can be found in the NOMAD Experiment-to-Archive Interface Control
424 Document (*EAI CD*, 2024). The results retrieved from the NOMAD SO measurements
425 presented in this work are being archived and available at (Brines et al., 2024).

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References

446

- 447 Alday, J., Trokhimovskiy, A., Irwin, P. G., Wilson, C. F., Montmessin, F., Lefèvre, F.,
 448 ... others (2021). Isotopic fractionation of water and its photolytic products in the
 449 atmosphere of mars. *Nature Astronomy*, *5*(9), 943–950.
- 450 Aoki, S., Vandaele, A., Daerden, F., Villanueva, G., Liuzzi, G., Thomas, I., ... others (2019).
 451 Water vapor vertical profiles on Mars in dust storms observed by TGO/NOMAD.
 452 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*.
- 453 Aoki, S., Vandaele, A. C., Daerden, F., Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Clancy, ... others
 454 (2022). Global vertical distribution of water vapor on Mars: Results from 3.5 years of
 455 ExoMars-TGO/NOMAD science operations.
- 456 Belyaev, D. A., Fedorova, A., Trokhimovskiy, A., Alday, J., Montmessin, F., Korablev,
 457 O. I., ... Shakun, A. V. (2021). Revealing a high water abundance in the upper
 458 mesosphere of Mars with ACS onboard TGO. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *48*(10),
 459 e2021GL093411.
- 460 Bhattacharyya, D., Clarke, J., Chaufray, J.-Y., Mayyasi, M., Bertaux, J.-L., Chaffin, M.,
 461 ... Villanueva, G. (2017). Seasonal changes in hydrogen escape from mars through
 462 analysis of hst observations of the martian exosphere near perihelion. *Journal of*
 463 *Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, *122*(11), 11–756.
- 464 Brines, A., López-Valverde, M., Funke, B., Galindo, F., Aoki, S., Villanueva, G., et al. (2024,
 465 March). Strong localized pumping of water vapor to high altitudes on Mars during
 466 the perihelion season [Dataset]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10779225>. doi:
 467 10.5281/zenodo.10779225
- 468 Brines, A., López-Valverde, M., Stolzenbach, A., Modak, A., Funke, B., Galindo, F., ...
 469 others (2023). Water vapor vertical distribution on mars during perihelion season
 470 of my 34 and my 35 with exomars-tgo/nomad observations. *Journal of Geophysical*
 471 *Research: Planets*, *128*(11), e2022JE007273.
- 472 Chaffin, M., Deighan, J., Schneider, N., & Stewart, A. (2017). Elevated atmospheric escape
 473 of atomic hydrogen from mars induced by high-altitude water. *Nature geoscience*,
 474 *10*(3), 174–178.
- 475 Clancy, R. T., Sandor, B. J., Wolff, M. J., Smith, M. D., Lefèvre, F., Madeleine, J.-B., ...
 476 others (2012). Extensive mro crism observations of 1.27 μm o₂ airglow in mars polar
 477 night and their comparison to mro mcs temperature profiles and lmd gcm simulations.
 478 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, *117*(E11).
- 479 Clancy, R. T., Smith, M. D., Lefèvre, F., McConnochie, T. H., Sandor, B. J., Wolff, M. J.,
 480 ... others (2017). Vertical profiles of mars 1.27 μm o₂ dayglow from mro crism limb
 481 spectra: Seasonal/global behaviors, comparisons to lmdgcm simulations, and a global
 482 definition for mars water vapor profiles. *Icarus*, *293*, 132–156.
- 483 Crismani, M., Villanueva, G., Liuzzi, G., Smith, M., Knutsen, E., Daerden, F., ...
 484 others (2021). A global and seasonal perspective of martian water vapor from
 485 exomars/nomad. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, *126*(11), e2021JE006878.
- 486 EAICD. (2024). [https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/ftp/ExoMars2016/em16_tgo](https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/ftp/ExoMars2016/em16_tgo_nmd/document/EAICD/)
 487 [_nmd/document/EAICD/](https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/ftp/ExoMars2016/em16_tgo_nmd/document/EAICD/). European Space Agency. (Dataset)
- 488 Fedorova, A., Bertaux, J.-L., Betsis, D., Montmessin, F., Korablev, O., Maltagliati, L., &
 489 Clarke, J. (2018). Water vapor in the middle atmosphere of Mars during the 2007
 490 global dust storm. *Icarus*, *300*, 440–457.
- 491 Fedorova, A., Korablev, O., Bertaux, J.-L., Rodin, A., Montmessin, F., Belyaev, D., &
 492 Reberac, A. (2009). Solar infrared occultation observations by spicam experiment
 493 on mars-express: Simultaneous measurements of the vertical distributions of h₂o, co₂
 494 and aerosol. *Icarus*, *200*(1), 96–117.
- 495 Fedorova, A., Montmessin, F., Korablev, O., Lefèvre, F., Trokhimovskiy, A., & Bertaux,
 496 J.-L. (2021). Multi-annual monitoring of the water vapor vertical distribution on
 497 mars by spicam on mars express. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, *126*(1),
 498 e2020JE006616.
- 499 Fedorova, A., Montmessin, F., Korablev, O., Luginin, M., Trokhimovskiy, A., Belyaev,
 500 D. A., ... others (2020). Stormy water on Mars: The distribution and saturation of

- atmospheric water during the dusty season. *Science*, 367(6475), 297–300.
- 501 Fedorova, A., Montmessin, F., Trokhimovskiy, A., Luginin, M., Korablev, O., Alday, J., ...
 502 others (2023). A two-martian years survey of the water vapor saturation state on mars
 503 based on acs nir/tgo occultations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 128(1),
 504 e2022JE007348.
 505
- 506 Forget, F., Hourdin, F., Fournier, R., Hourdin, C., Talagrand, O., Collins, M., ... Huot,
 507 J.-P. (1999). Improved general circulation models of the Martian atmosphere from
 508 the surface to above 80 km. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 104(E10),
 509 24155–24175.
- 510 Gamache, R. R., Faresse, M., & Renaud, C. L. (2016). A spectral line list for water
 511 isotopologues in the 1100–4100 cm⁻¹ region for application to co₂-rich planetary
 512 atmospheres. *Journal of Molecular Spectroscopy*, 326, 144–150.
- 513 Gordon, I. E., Rothman, L. S., Hargreaves, R., Hashemi, R., Karlovets, E. V., Skinner,
 514 F., ... others (2022). The hitran2020 molecular spectroscopic database. *Journal of*
 515 *quantitative spectroscopy and radiative transfer*, 277, 107949.
- 516 Gundlach, B., Skorov, Y. V., & Blum, J. (2011). Outgassing of icy bodies in the solar
 517 system–i. the sublimation of hexagonal water ice through dust layers. *Icarus*, 213(2),
 518 710–719.
- 519 Heavens, N. G., Kleinböhl, A., Chaffin, M. S., Halekas, J. S., Kass, D. M., Hayne, P. O., ...
 520 Schofield, J. T. (2018). Hydrogen escape from Mars enhanced by deep convection in
 521 dust storms. *Nature Astronomy*, 2(2), 126–132.
- 522 Holmes, J., Lewis, S., Patel, M., Alday, J., Aoki, S., Liuzzi, G., ... others (2022). Global
 523 variations in water vapor and saturation state throughout the mars year 34 dusty
 524 season. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 127(10), e2022JE007203.
- 525 Holmes, J., Lewis, S., Patel, M., Chaffin, M., Cangi, E., Deighan, J., ... others (2021).
 526 Enhanced water loss from the martian atmosphere during a regional-scale dust storm
 527 and implications for long-term water loss. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 571,
 528 117109.
- 529 Jakosky, B. M. (2021). Atmospheric loss to space and the history of water on mars. *Annual*
 530 *Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 49, 71–93.
- 531 Jiménez-Monferrer, S., López-Valverde, M. Á., Funke, B., González-Galindo, F., Piccialli,
 532 A., García-Comas, M., ... Bibring, J.-P. (2021). CO₂ retrievals in the Mars daylight
 533 thermosphere from its 4.3 μm limb emission measured by OMEGA/MEx. *Icarus*, 353,
 534 113830.
- 535 Kass, D., Schofield, J., Kleinböhl, A., McCleese, D., Heavens, N., Shirley, J., & Steele, L.
 536 (2020). Mars climate sounder observation of mars’ 2018 global dust storm. *Geophysical*
 537 *Research Letters*, 47(23), e2019GL083931.
- 538 Kuntz, M. (1997). A new implementation of the humlicek algorithm for the calculation of the
 539 voigt profile function. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*,
 540 57(6), 819–824.
- 541 Liuzzi, G., Villanueva, G. L., Mumma, M. J., Smith, M. D., Daerden, F., Ristic, B., ...
 542 others (2019). Methane on Mars: New insights into the sensitivity of CH₄ with the
 543 NOMAD/ExoMars spectrometer through its first in-flight calibration. *Icarus*, 321,
 544 671–690.
- 545 Lopez-Valverde, M. A., Funke, B., Brines, A., Stolzenbach, A., Modak, A., Gonzalez-
 546 Galindo, F., et al. (2022). Martian atmospheric temperature and density profiles
 547 during the 1st year of NOMAD/TGO solar occultation measurements.
- 548 Maltagliati, L., Montmessin, F., Fedorova, A., Korablev, O., Forget, F., & Bertaux, J.-L.
 549 (2011). Evidence of water vapor in excess of saturation in the atmosphere of Mars.
 550 *science*, 333(6051), 1868–1871.
- 551 Maltagliati, L., Montmessin, F., Korablev, O., Fedorova, A., Forget, F., Määttänen, A.,
 552 ... Bertaux, J.-L. (2013). Annual survey of water vapor vertical distribution and
 553 water–aerosol coupling in the martian atmosphere observed by SPICAM/MEx solar
 554 occultations. *Icarus*, 223(2), 942–962.

- 555 Martín-Rubio, C., Vicente-Retortillo, A., Gómez, F., & Rodríguez-Manfredi, J. (2024).
 556 Interannual variability of regional dust storms between mars years 24 and 36. *Icarus*,
 557 *412*, 115982.
- 558 Mayyasi, M., Clarke, J., Chaufray, J.-Y., Kass, D., Bougher, S., Bhattacharyya, D., ...
 559 others (2023). Solar cycle and seasonal variability of h in the upper atmosphere of
 560 mars. *Icarus*, *393*, 115293.
- 561 Montmessin, F., Belyaev, D. A., Lefèvre, F., Alday, J., Vals, M., Fedorova, A., ... Schneider,
 562 N. M. (2022). Reappraising the production and transfer of hydrogen atoms from the
 563 middle to the upper atmosphere of mars at times of elevated water vapor. *Journal of*
 564 *Geophysical Research: Planets*, *127*(5), e2022JE007217.
- 565 Montmessin, F., Smith, M. D., Langevin, Y., Mellon, M. T., & Fedorova, A. (2017). The
 566 water cycle. *The atmosphere and climate of Mars*, *18*, 338.
- 567 Neary, L., Daerden, F., Aoki, S., Whiteway, J., Clancy, R. T., Smith, M., ... others
 568 (2020). Explanation for the increase in high-altitude water on Mars observed by
 569 NOMAD during the 2018 global dust storm. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *47*(7),
 570 e2019GL084354.
- 571 Pankine, A. A., Leung, C., Tamppari, L., Martinez, G., Giuranna, M., Piqueux, S., ...
 572 Trokhimovskiy, A. (2023). Effects of global dust storms on water vapor in the
 573 southern polar region of mars. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, *128*(12),
 574 e2023JE008016.
- 575 Poncin, L., Kleinböhl, A., Kass, D. M., Clancy, R. T., Aoki, S., & Vandaele, A. C. (2022).
 576 Water vapor saturation and ice cloud occurrence in the atmosphere of mars. *Planetary*
 577 *and Space Science*, *212*, 105390.
- 578 PSA. (2024). [https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/#!Table%20View/NOMAD=](https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/#!Table%20View/NOMAD=instrument)
 579 [instrument](https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/#!Table%20View/NOMAD=instrument). European Space Agency. (Dataset)
- 580 Rodin, A., Korablev, O., & Moroz, V. (1997). Vertical distribution of water in the near-
 581 equatorial troposphere of mars: Water vapor and clouds. *Icarus*, *125*(1), 212–229.
- 582 Ruyten, W. (2004). Comment on “a new implementation of the humlicek algorithm for
 583 the calculation of the voigt profile function” by m. kuntz [jqsrt 57 (6)(1997) 819–824].
 584 *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, *86*(2), 231–233.
- 585 Shaposhnikov, D. S., Medvedev, A. S., Rodin, A. V., & Hartogh, P. (2019). Seasonal
 586 water “pump” in the atmosphere of Mars: Vertical transport to the thermosphere.
 587 *Geophysical Research Letters*, *46*(8), 4161–4169.
- 588 Smith, M. D. (2002). The annual cycle of water vapor on Mars as observed by the Thermal
 589 Emission Spectrometer. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, *107*(E11), 25–1.
- 590 Smith, M. D., Bougher, S. W., Encrenaz, T., Forget, F., & Kleinböhl, A. (2017). Thermal
 591 structure and composition. *The atmosphere and climate of Mars*, *18*, 42.
- 592 Stiller, G. P., von Clarmann, T., Funke, B., Glatthor, N., Hase, F., Höpfner, M., & Linden,
 593 A. (2002). Sensitivity of trace gas abundances retrievals from infrared limb emission
 594 spectra to simplifying approximations in radiative transfer modelling. *Journal of*
 595 *Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, *72*(3), 249–280.
- 596 Streeter, P. M., Lewis, S. R., Patel, M. R., Holmes, J. A., Fedorova, A. A., Kass, D. M., &
 597 Kleinböhl, A. (2021). Asymmetric impacts on mars’ polar vortices from an equinoctial
 598 global dust storm. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, *126*(5), e2020JE006774.
- 599 Thomas, I. R., Aoki, S., Trompet, L., Robert, S., Depiesse, C., Willame, Y., ... others
 600 (2022). Calibration of nomad on esa’s exomars trace gas orbiter: Part 1—the solar
 601 occultation channel. *Planetary and Space Science*, *218*, 105411.
- 602 Trompet, L., Vandaele, A., Thomas, I., Aoki, S., Daerden, F., Erwin, J., ... others
 603 (2023). Carbon dioxide retrievals from nomad-so on esa’s exomars trace gas orbiter
 604 and temperature profiles retrievals with the hydrostatic equilibrium equation: 1.
 605 description of the method. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, *128*(3),
 606 e2022JE007277.
- 607 Vandaele, A. C., De Mazière, M., Drummond, R., Mahieux, A., Neefs, E., Wilquet, V., ...
 608 others (2008). Composition of the venus mesosphere measured by solar occultation at
 609 infrared on board venus express. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, *113*(E5).

- 610 Vandaele, A. C., Korabiev, O., Daerden, F., Aoki, S., Thomas, I. R., Altieri, F., ... others
611 (2019). Martian dust storm impact on atmospheric h₂o and d/h observed by exomars
612 trace gas orbiter. *Nature*, *568*(7753), 521–525.
- 613 Vandaele, A. C., Kruglanski, M., & De Mazière, M. (2006). Modeling and retrieval of
614 atmospheric spectra using asimut..
- 615 Vandaele, A. C., Lopez-Moreno, J.-J., Patel, M. R., Bellucci, G., Daerden, F., Ristic, B., ...
616 others (2018). NOMAD, an integrated suite of three spectrometers for the ExoMars
617 trace gas mission: Technical description, science objectives and expected performance.
618 *Space Science Reviews*, *214*(5), 1–47. Retrieved from [https://doi.org/10.1007/
619 s11214-018-0517-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-018-0517-2)
- 620 Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Aoki, S. W., Shohei adn Stone, Brines, A., Thomas, I. R.,
621 Lopez-Valverde, M. A., ... others (2022). The deuterium isotopic ratio of water
622 released from the Martian caps as measured with TGO/NOMAD.
- 623 Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Crismani, M. M., Aoki, S., Vandaele, A. C., Daerden, F.,
624 ... others (2021). Water heavily fractionated as it ascends on Mars as revealed by
625 ExoMars/NOMAD. *Science Advances*, *7*(7), eabc8843.
- 626 Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Faggi, S., Protopapa, S., Kofman, V., Fauchez, T., ... Mandell,
627 A. M. (2022). Fundamentals of the planetary spectrum generator. *Fundamentals of
628 the Planetary Spectrum Generator. 2022 edition of the handbook by GL Villanueva et
629 al. ISBN 978-0-578-36143-7.*
- 630 Villanueva, G. L., Smith, M. D., Protopapa, S., Faggi, S., & Mandell, A. M.
631 (2018). Planetary spectrum generator: An accurate online radiative transfer suite
632 for atmospheres, comets, small bodies and exoplanets. *Journal of Quantitative
633 Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, *217*, 86–104.
- 634 von Clarmann, v., Glatthor, N., Grabowski, U., Höpfner, M., Kellmann, S., Kiefer,
635 M., ... others (2003). Retrieval of temperature and tangent altitude pointing
636 from limb emission spectra recorded from space by the michelson interferometer for
637 passive atmospheric sounding (mipas). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*,
638 *108*(D23).